

RESEARCH DATA RETENTION AND DISPOSAL: OVERVIEW AND GUIDELINES

WORK PACKAGE 4: BIG-DATA ELECTRON AND CORRELATIVE MICROSCOPY FROM INSTRUMENT TO PUBLICATION

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Executive summary

In the era of big data, keeping all data or copies of data unselectively has become unrealistic or unreasonable for many research organisations. Knowing what data to keep, how to store them and for how long is essential but can be challenging. Beyond the retention and disposal of research data mandated by legislation and funding bodies, suitable practices in research data retention and disposal can play a fundamental role in making data storage sustainable and ensuring that data remain valuable, authentic and compatible with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and CARE (Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility and Ethics) data principles. They also enhance the discoverability, sharing and reuse of research data. In this report, eight recommendations are proposed to provide microscopy research facilities with guidance and foster best practices in research data retention and disposal. These recommendations are based on a survey of the facilities on their awareness and practices in data retention and disposal, and focus on key elements:

Recommendation 1: Data retention policy

Every facility should develop a data retention policy that details the rules and protocols for retaining and disposing of their users' data, in particular by addressing what data to retain, how to retain data and when to dispose of data.

Recommendation 2: Data disposal — Extended retention of users' data

Every facility should eliminate their users' data after users have retrieved their data, unless the data retention policy of the facility describes explicitly and transparently how long users' data are retained for after users' experiments.

Recommendation 3: Data disposal — Suitable protocol for data elimination

Facilities should use appropriate methods to eliminate data, in particular in the case of sensitive data.

Recommendation 4: Data security and access to users' data

When facilities retain users' data, they should ensure that data remain accurate, complete and unaltered, and are accessible and available to authorised people only.

Recommendation 5: Storage of users' data

Facilities that store users' data should ensure that the purpose of the storage (backup, temporary retention, archive) is described in their data retention policies and communicated to their users.

Recommendation 6: Sustainable file formats

Data should be stored in sustainable file formats from their point of capture or creation in order to minimise the risk of information loss over time.

Recommendation 7: Metadata collection

Metadata should be collected throughout the data lifecycle to facilitate and assist in the data curation, retention (storage, access control, sharing, reuse) and disposal.

Recommendation 8: Research data management plan

Facility users should have research data management plans that describe the conditions for the storage, retention, disposal, access control and sharing of their data by facilities.

This work was undertaken under Work Package 4: “Big-data electron and correlative microscopy from instrument to publication” of the Australian Characterisation Commons at Scale (ACCS) project.

1 Introduction

As innovations and technical breakthroughs in the tools used in research and notably in microscopy enable the generation of large volumes of data at ever-growing resolution, scale and speed, single experiments can routinely lead to data from tens of gigabytes to a few terabytes in size [1, 2]. Although the simultaneous expansion of big data in science and the growing awareness of the FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable data) have created unique opportunities for research [3], their combination constitutes immense and unprecedented challenges for researchers and institutions in terms of continuing and sustainable data management and storage to support the discoverability and availability of data for sharing and reuse [4]. Unmanaged data are a loss of opportunity for new collaborations and lessen the impact of research projects, researchers and research organisations involved. A 2019 report of the European Commission estimated that the overall cost of not having FAIR research data amounted to at least €10.2 bn per year in the European Union [5]. Non-FAIR-compliant data were found to have a significant impact on researchers' times (for example, in time spent or lost to locate and access data, to authenticate and assess the quality of data, and to understand, curate, cleanse and reprocess incomplete data or incompletely or wrongly described data) and storage costs (for example, storage of multiple copies of data on different repositories and storage of data wrongly or insufficiently described to be identified or accessible). Beyond the promotion of the benefits of the FAIR principles, this study demonstrated that the adoption of policies and best practices in research data retention supported by organisational strategies was central to maintain the long-term value, quality and accessibility of stored data.

Data retention refers to the practice of storing and managing data for a given, predetermined period of time beyond the completion of a research project in order to fulfil legislative, ethical, sectoral and contractual obligations of the researcher (or researchers) who conducted the project and the institution (or institutions) involved in the project. Identifying what research data to keep is as important as retaining them to ensure the sustainability of data archiving and accessibility of data. A lack of planning or execution in the retention or disposal of research data can be associated with inappropriate description and archiving of data, thereby impeding data and research from realising their maximum value and impact. This may require a cultural change across research institutions, researchers and research-funding agencies [6]. Furthermore, while data storage may be getting cheaper, in particular with the development of cloud computing, the total cost of data upkeep throughout the lifetime of a project and beyond to adhere to a range of business requirements (laws, regulations, guidelines), is climbing rapidly. The common practice of keeping all data supporting a research project unselectively including multiple variations of the processed and analysed data must therefore be questioned in light of sustainability, feasibility and cost.

In this report, general concepts in record-keeping and research data retention and disposal are introduced, including concepts mentioned above such as data archiving and curation. The legislative landscape that governs the retention and disposal of research data at the federal, state and territory levels as well as abroad is briefly outlined alongside an overview of some sectoral requirements specific to scientific research. General observations on policies concerning research data retention and disposal across universities are presented. The level

of awareness on research data retention and disposal across microscopy facilities in Australia and how that was translated into local practices was examined through a survey. The outcome of the survey is described and discussed. Finally, general recommendations on various aspects of research data retention and disposal—specifically retention, disposal, security and access, storage, file formats, description and research data management planning—are proposed to promote best practices and ensure the discoverability and reuse of research data. Ultimately, best practices in the retention and disposal of research data underpin the FAIR principles [3] and the CARE principles for Indigenous data governance (Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility and Ethics) [7].

This work was undertaken under the Australian Characterisation Commons at Scale (ACCS) project, in particular under Work Package 4: “Big-data electron and correlative microscopy from instrument to publication”. This report is intended as the conclusion of the work planned for deliverable WP4.10: “Develop a common set of best practices for data retention and disposal”.

2 General concepts in research data retention and disposal

Data retention is closely linked to a range of key concepts such as information, records, archives, record-keeping, retention period, disposal, appraisal, retention schedule, storage, curation and preservation. They are briefly described below.

2.1 Data, information, record and archive

Practices in data retention and disposal are largely inherited from, and often combined with, those in information management, records management and archive management. It is common for institutions to establish policies and procedures for records or information management, including retention and disposal, that extend to research data explicitly or implicitly. It can therefore be useful to understand the differences between the concepts of data, information, records and archives. Below are working definitions for those terms, noting that disciplines, business sectors and organisations may choose alternative definitions.

Data are the product of observations or measurements. Data may be qualitative or quantitative; physical or digital; textual, numeric, graphic (as a single image or a sequence of images as in a video), acoustic or multimedia; structured or unstructured; processed or unprocessed [8, 9, 10]. Unlike unstructured data, structured data are formatted to a predefined and consistent field structure. They are easily readable by machines. The concept of dataset is sometimes conflated with that of data. A common definition used here and relevant to microscopy is that a dataset is a structured collection or aggregation of data that are generally associated with a unique body of work or a particular subject, or created for a specific purpose (for example, an experiment) [10]. A dataset can contain several files or folders.

Information is inferred from data. It is data in a particular context (for example, in a processed or communicated form) for a particular purpose [11]. As the concepts of data and information overlap, some organisations use them interchangeably (in policies, procedures etc.).

A record is information created, received and maintained in the course of a business or personal activity. It provides evidence of the work, actions and decisions. It is an asset that

can be a tangible object or digital information [9, 12]. The *Management of Research Data and Records Policy (MPF1242)* at The University of Melbourne provides a list of records associated with research: “correspondence (including electronic mail as well as paper-based correspondence); project files; grant applications; ethics applications; authorship agreements; technical reports; research reports; laboratory notebooks or research journals; master lists; signed consent forms; and information sheets for research participants” [13].

Archives are a subset of records. They are kept permanently for their continuing value because they may be necessary for ongoing purposes to their creator or because they have additional research value [9, 12]. The value of a record may be legal, administrative, financial, social, cultural or historical. Archiving a record implies that its integrity, security, authenticity and accessibility are maintained over time [14].

The distinction between data, record and archive is not as rigid as their definitions may suggest. Data are assets in a research activity and may thus be considered as an extension of records. The separation between records and archives can also be fuzzy as yesterday’s archive may become today’s record if a material is reused in a research work. As a result, the management of records is not limited to successive stages in a linear, unidirectional course of actions. Actions on a record may be simultaneous: a record may be active and accessed for current organisational purposes and at the same time archived [9].

For the sake of clarity, the terms *data*, *information* and *records* will be used interchangeably in this report when referring to research data.

2.2 Record-keeping

Record-keeping consists in making and maintaining complete, accurate and reliable evidence of business transactions. It encompasses the management and archiving of records [15, 16].

2.3 Data retention period

The retention period of a piece of data is the mandatory period of time that this piece needs to be kept for to meet administrative, legislative, fiscal, sectoral, business and community (for example, historical, societal, cultural) requirements before its final disposal [17, 18]. Research-funding bodies and publishers may have their own expectations regarding the retention period of data associated with funded projects and publications, respectively. The retention period is often understood as the *minimum* period over which data must be stored. There is often no obligation to eliminate data after their retention periods have elapsed.

2.4 Data disposal

Disposal (or disposition) is the range of documented processes that take place after expiration of the data retention period. It encompasses two types of actions outlined schematically in Figure 1, and resulting in either the relocation of data or their elimination. Here, the terms *relocation* and *elimination* are used as generic, neutral words because many terms associated with disposal (for example, destruction) have a specific meaning.

Data relocation consists of two activities:

- archiving: the permanent (that is, perpetual) retention of data as national, state,

territory or public archives, or archives of the organisation; or

- the transfer of custodianship and/or ownership of data to another entity, such as a person or a government jurisdiction, usually after expiration of a retention period.

In neither case does the initial data custodian or owner keep a copy of the data after relocation.

Data elimination is the deliberate removal of data from their storage medium (for example, hard drive, laptop), usually after a retention period. It involves various processes, including data destruction, data erasure, cryptographic erasure, data masking, data deletion, reformatting of the data storage device, factory reset of the storage device and data wiping (or file shredding) [19, 20]. These processes have different implications in terms of security and persistence of the data after elimination (Figure 1). Specifically, data destruction, data erasure, cryptographic erasure and data masking are secure processes that lead to the permanent, irreversible action of eliminating data from the storage device. They render data irretrievable even with the assistance of advanced forensic tools. They are collectively referred to as data sanitisation. In contrast, with data deletion, data wiping, reformatting of the data storage device and factory reset of the storage device, data can remain recoverable and readable after the completion of these actions or there is no verification that the process was successful in removing data [20]. In some cases, the elimination of data containing personal information can be completed by de-identifying the data [21]. Data masking presents key advantages compared to other data sanitisation methods. It is quick and easy to implement, is widely used in compliance strategies and explicitly required by some standards and regulations to protect sensitive data, such as the *General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)* that protects personal data in the European Union and the *Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPPA)* in the United States that regulates the use and disclosure of protected health information [22, 23].

Disposal is undertaken after a predetermined, specified trigger. A trigger is an event from which the disposal date is calculated. The Australasian Digital Recordkeeping Initiative distinguishes a range of triggers for the disposal of records [24]:

- completion of an action;
- appointment date of a person;
- creation date of records;
- date of birth or death of a person;
- disposition or decommissioning date of an asset;
- issue date or expiry date of a policy or legal document;
- end of a reference use;
- separation date of an employee from an organisation;
- supersession date of a document; and
- termination date of a policy or legal agreement.

Some jurisdictions or organisations may use alternative or additional triggers (for example, the end of the financial year). In the case of research data, the disposal trigger can be the completion of a funded project or a publication out of a project.

A range of factors determine how and when research data may be disposed of. Specifically, in addition to legislative requirements, research data may be subject to community expectations

Figure 1 Schematic description of data relocation and data elimination in the data disposal process.

(general public and research communities) and obligations to funding bodies, collaborators (in particular commercial partners) and publishers. Furthermore, external factors can interfere with the retention period. For example, data may be involved in a disposal-freeze directive (in the

case of a prominent or controversial issue or event, or because of judicial proceeding), an audit or an access-to-information request. Each external factor is associated with a retention requirement. The common rule is that data are kept for the period of time that is the longest between their normal retention period (calculated from the disposal trigger) and the various applicable extraordinary retention requirements.

2.5 Data appraisal and records retention schedule

A key activity in record-keeping is appraisal, that is to determine what data to keep, how to keep them and how long to keep them for [25]. Data retention and data disposal are thus inherently linked. A records retention schedule (also called disposal schedule, disposal authority, retention and disposal schedule, or retention and disposal authority) is a document that gives an organisation the information and the power to make decisions about the disposal of its data. It guides appraisal. A records retention schedule involves three elements:

- the retention period: how long records and data must be kept for;
- the disposal action: what happens after the retention period has lapsed; and
- the disposal trigger: when the disposal action happens.

By its very nature, a records retention schedule authorises an organisation to destroy data in specific cases. Note, this report focuses on records retention schedules issued by Australian governments (Commonwealth, state and territories) but organisations can also establish their own records retention schedules to meet their legal and operational obligations.

In general, the minimum period for retention of research data is 5 years from the date of publication. However, specific types of research data such as those linked to clinical trials and gene therapy may be retained for a longer period. An example is given in Table 1 that lists the disposal actions and retention periods for research data described in the *General retention and disposal authority: higher and further education (GA47)* for public universities in New South Wales [26]. As can be seen, the retention period for research data varies from 5 years to perpetuity depending on the research class. In the case of short-term research projects that are for assessment purposes only (for example, students' research projects), retaining research data for 12 months after the completion of the project may be sufficient [27].

2.6 Data storage

Retaining data temporarily or permanently means providing an appropriate physical medium to store data. In particular, the integrity, accessibility and availability of the stored data must be maintained throughout the whole retention period. Improper storage contributes to the loss of data or the inability to share or access data over time (a situation sometimes referred to as "data decay") [28]. Compromises in confidentiality, integrity and availability of data are associated with the following risks [29]:

- data confidentiality: risk of unauthorised or inappropriate disclosure of data;
- data integrity: risk of unauthorised or accidental modification of data; and
- data availability: risk of inability to access or read data.

Devices or facilities used for data storage must thus ensure that data remain [30, 31]:

Table 1 Disposal of research records and data at public universities in New South Wales. Based on the *General retention and disposal authority: higher and further education (GA47)* (section 3.5.0) [26].

Description of records	Disposal action
<p>Data and datasets created as part of research activities within the institution, which are of <i>regulatory or community significance</i>. Includes data created that are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • part of genetic research; • controversial or of high public interest, or has influence in the research domain; • costly or impossible to reproduce or substitute if the primary data are not available; • related to the use of an innovative technique for the first time; • of significant community or heritage value to the state or nation; or • required by funding or other agreements to be retained permanently. 	<p>Required as State archives.</p>
<p>Data and datasets created from clinical trials, or research with potential long-term effects on humans, as part of research activities within the institution, which are <i>not of regulatory or community significance</i> (including animal testing for human products).</p>	<p>Retain minimum of 15 years after completion of research activity or until subject reaches or would have reached the age of 25 years, whichever is longer, then destroy.</p>
<p>Data and datasets created as part of research activities within the institution which do not involve clinical trials, research with potential long-term effects on humans, gene therapy or which are <i>not of regulatory or community significance</i>.</p>	<p>Retain minimum of 5 years after project completed, then destroy.</p>

- authentic, accurate and trusted: data are stored in a known, trusted location (or via a known, trusted medium) and remain correct, and their access is monitored;
- complete and unaltered: data remain comprehensive and immutable, that is none of the information is missing as a result of a modification, truncation or damage;
- secure: data are protected from unauthorised access, corruption, deletion or theft; and
- findable and readable: the location of data remain available and accessible for as long as necessary for both machines and humans.

Data archiving and more broadly data retention are often taken as a synonym for backup whereas the two types of storage activities are distinct and serve separate purposes. Figure 2 highlights the main differences between data retention and backup. With data retention, data that will not change (inactive and immutable data) are moved to a dedicated long-term storage medium for a finite period of time or in perpetuity in order to meet very specific legislative or compliance obligations while the discoverability, accessibility, integrity and availability of data are maintained. This also has the benefit of freeing up storage resources for new and active

Figure 2 Differences between data backup and data retention.

data. In contrast, with backup, working data are replicated to another storage medium or location so that the backup can be used to restore data in their original form in the event of a system failure or disaster that would cause loss, corruption, damage or error in the data. The same data can be backed up multiple times and periodically so that data can be recovered in different past states at different points in time (for example, as in Time Machine in macOS). Fundamentally, data retention is part of a data retention policy whereas data backup is integral to a disaster recovery plan. Note, retained data may be backed up to create redundancy in the storage system that ensures the integrity of data in case of an incident or a cyberattack.

2.7 Data curation and preservation

Data curation and preservation maintain the value of data from their creation.

Data curation encompasses a range of activities in data management and analysis. It refers to the actions that maintain, preserve and enhance the use or reuse value of data throughout their lifecycle while mitigating the risk of digital obsolescence. For example, data collected from various sources can be aggregated or integrated into a single dataset that may be more valuable than its independent parts. During curation, data may be annotated, tagged, reorganised, reformatted or published for various purposes, including the production of new scientific knowledge, the reproduction of existing results to ensure scientific integrity and the calibration of scientific instruments. The goal is to keep the data valuable so that it can be reused in as many applications as possible [32, 33].

Data preservation is the collection of measures taken by an organisation to ensure the

accessibility, authenticity, integrity and usability of retained data over time, whether data are retained temporarily or permanently (i.e. archived). Those measures encompass both digital (for example, the choice of the file formats) and physical (for example, the temperature and humidity control in a data store facility) actions. Some research data are unique and cannot be replaced if destroyed, corrupted or lost. The technological obsolescence of storage hardware and associated software poses significant risks to the fate of retained data, in particular in the case of long-term retention and archive. It is especially important when data are required to be kept for a period that exceeds the longevities of storage media, both hardware and software [34]. Therefore, the preservation of data plays an important role in an organisation's strategy for data retention and archiving.

3 Research data retention and disposal in the data lifecycle

The different stages that research data go through from initial creation (for example, from capture from a microscope) to eventual archiving, destruction or reuse, are described in a research data lifecycle. Different models for the research data lifecycle have been proposed but, in all models, every stage is associated with decisions and responsibilities related to data. Figure 3 shows a research data lifecycle adapted from the data roadmap proposed by Briney [35] and to which data curation, appraisal and elimination have been added. Overall, the stages that play essential roles in the retention and disposal of research data are:

- research planning (project and data management): strategies for the management of the research project and data generated throughout the project are designed concurrently, and a research data management plan is created;
- publication, data sharing and appraisal: data can be shared in many ways, for example, with collaborators or in public repositories. In any case, the modalities for data access must be defined. Appraisal plays a critical role by identifying responsibilities for data retention and disposal, including who owns or manages data (data owner, custodian, steward or manager), what data to retain and for how long;
- data preservation: the retention of data requires strategies that maintain the value and accessibility of data despite the change and obsolescence of technologies, such as hardware and software used to store and read data, respectively;
- data curation: at every stage of the lifecycle data can be curated to keep, increase or promote their value; and
- data elimination: data that are not retained are eliminated. Data elimination is the necessary mirror action of data retention.

As depicted in Figure 3, considerations on the appropriate storage of data are integral to the data lifecycle. The types of data generated through a research project (for example, non-sensitive, commercial or clinical data) can determine for a large part the conditions for their disposal and retention, the type of storage to use and the level of security to store them under throughout the research project and beyond.

Figure 3 Representation of the research data lifecycle coupled with the data storage, curation and security cycles. The stages that are important for data retention and disposal are outlined in black. Adapted from [35].

4 Legislative record-keeping and disposal requirements

There is no legislation at the federal, state or territory level that governs the retention and disposal of research data specifically. Instead, retention and disposal of research data are covered by state or territory legislation on records and information management, except for Commonwealth agencies that are under Commonwealth jurisdiction. A range of legislative acts may be applicable to records and information management. For example, Monash University provides a non-exhaustive list of Commonwealth and Victorian state laws that can impact record-keeping in Victoria, thereby demonstrating the complexity of the matter: *Crimes Act 1958* (Vic), *Evidence Act 1958* (Vic), *Copyright Act 1968* (Cth), *Public Records Act 1973* (Vic), *Freedom of Information Act 1982* (Vic), *Privacy Act 1988* (Cth), *Information Privacy Act 2000* (Vic), *Electronic Transactions Act 2001* (Cth), *Health Records Act 2001* (Vic) and *Whistleblowers Protection Act 2001* (Vic) [36].

Research data retention and disposal are addressed in records retention schedules. The Commonwealth, states and territories have developed their own record-keeping and disposal requirements that identify classes of records (including data). The categorisation of records, the retention periods for record categories and the disposal actions may differ across jurisdictions. They may also vary across Commonwealth agencies. This review will therefore be limited to outlining general features to consider on research data retention and disposal. In the case of health and clinical data, special requirements related to human and animal ethics

need to be considered. For example, provisions in the *Therapeutic Goods Regulations 1990* (Cth) [37] and the *Guideline for Good Clinical Practice ICH E6(R2)* [38] apply to data from clinical trials. However, there may be additional state or territory requirements based on criteria such as the location of data collection and the age of research participants. For example, some states and territories may differentiate clinical research data on adults from those on minors.

4.1 Commonwealth

Despite the lack of federal legislation specific to the retention and disposal of all research data, some federal laws can apply to research data in specific contexts. Notable examples include the *Privacy Act 1988* (Cth) [39] and the *Archives Act 1983* (Cth) [40].

The *Privacy Act 1988* (Cth) [39] is the principal piece of legislation protecting the handling of personal information about individuals. It includes the collection, use, storage and disclosure of personal information in the federal public sector and the private sector. The act does not cover state or territory government agencies (including a state and territory public hospital or health care facility, with exceptions) or universities (except private universities and, notably, The Australian National University) amongst other exceptions. The Australian National University falls under the *Privacy Act* because it is a Commonwealth agency instituted by federal legislation (*Australian National University Act 1991* (Cth) [41]). A range of national organisations with research activities are also Commonwealth agencies bound by the act. Examples include: the Australian Centre for International Agricultural Research (ACIAR); the Australian Institute of Marine Science (AIMS); the Australian Nuclear Science and Technology Organisation (ANSTO); the Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO); the Cotton Research and Development Corporation (CRDC); the Fisheries Research and Development Corporation (FRDC); Geoscience Australia; the Grains Research and Development Corporation (GRDC); the Great Barrier Reef Marine Park Authority (GBRMPA); and Wine Australia. A list of Commonwealth agencies is available online.¹

The *Archives Act 1983* (Cth) [40] details the record-keeping requirements for Commonwealth records set out and overseen by the National Archives of Australia. Commonwealth records include records of Commonwealth agencies such as The Australian National University and CSIRO. Note, the *Archives Act* does not prescribe any specific retention period for any class of records. Instead, the National Archives issue records retention schedules called “records authorities” or “records disposal authorities” to individual agencies. As a Commonwealth agency, the research-associated functions of The Australian National University are covered by the *Records Authority – Australian National University 2006/00446555* [42].

4.2 States and territories

As agencies of their respective state or territory, public universities have record-keeping responsibilities governed by a records management act in their state and territory. Note, since The Australian National University is a Commonwealth agency, it is not concerned by the *Territory Records Act 2002* (ACT). The records retention schedules applicable to research data

¹ <https://www.directory.gov.au/departments-and-agencies>

at public universities in all states and territories are listed in Table 2.

4.3 Foreign legislation

Some aspects of record-keeping may be subject to foreign laws or regulations. In particular, the *General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)* of the European Union (EU) covers personal

Table 2 List of the records retention schedules applicable to research data at public universities in all states and territories.

Jurisdiction	Principal law(s) on record-keeping	Record-keeping agency	Retention schedule for research data
Australian Capital Territory	<i>Territory Records Act 2002</i> (ACT) [43]	Territory Records Office	<u><i>Records Disposal Schedule – Tertiary Teaching and Research Records</i></u> [44]
New South Wales	<i>State Records Act 1998</i> (NSW) [45]	NSW State Archives and Records	<u><i>General retention and disposal authority: higher and further education (GA47)</i></u> [26]
Northern Territory	<i>Information Act 2002</i> (NT) [46]	Northern Territory Archives Services	<u><i>Disposal Schedule for Research Management Records of the Charles Darwin University (No. 2017/14)</i></u> [47]
Queensland	<i>Public Records Act 2002</i> (Qld) [48]	Queensland State Archives	<u><i>University Sector Retention and Disposal Schedule (QDAN 601v.3)</i></u> [49]
South Australia	<i>State Records Act 1997</i> (SA) [50]	State Records of South Australia	<u><i>General Disposal Schedule No. 24 for Universities of South Australia (GDS 24)</i></u> [51]
Tasmania	<i>Archives Act 1983</i> (Tas) [52]	Tasmanian Archive and Heritage Office	<u><i>Disposal Schedule for Functional records of the University of Tasmania (DA 2398)</i></u> [53]
Victoria	<i>Public Records Act 1973</i> (Vic) [54]	Public Record Office Victoria	<u><i>Retention and Disposal Authority for Records of Higher and Further Education Functions (authority number: PROS 16/07)</i></u> [55]
Western Australia	<i>State Records Act 2000</i> (WA) [56]	State Records Office of Western Australia	<u><i>Western Australia University Sector Disposal Authority (Disposal Authority No 2022-005)</i></u> [57]

data of EU citizens and residents and applies to any organisation that handles such data, regardless of whether it is located in the EU or not [22]. The definition of personal data in the GDPR includes data derived from physical, physiological, medical, genetic and clinical information, and information related to an identifier such as any kind of identification number, location data and Internet Protocol address (IP address). Note, the analysis of body part or bodily substance (such as human biological samples) may lead to information that can be considered as personal data. Importantly, the regulation applies to the processing of personal data, where processing means “*any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction*”. The GDPR is applicable to all scientific research involving data that can identify an individual (personal data). Australian researchers who use, create or generate data derived from data or samples from the EU or obtained from collaborators in the EU might thus be required to follow specific procedures for the retention and disposal of their research data.

5 Sectoral requirements in research data retention and disposal

In addition to legislative requirements, publicly funded research is governed by codes, conventions and guidelines that define sectoral standards and best practices in the retention and disposal of research data. The *Australian Code for Responsible Conduct of Research (2018)* [58] is the cornerstone of best practices in publicly funded research.

Compliance with sectoral requirements often rests upon self-regulation, that is, researchers and research institutions are expected to conform to these requirements to receive, or be eligible to receive, research funding. There is thus no external and independent agency that monitors adherence to sectoral standards. For example, the National Health and Medical Research Council (NHMRC) requires that institutions receiving NHMRC funds “*attest annually to the NHMRC in writing that their research governance and ethical oversight processes remain compliant with [the] National Statement [on Ethical Conduct in Human Research 2007 (updated 2018)] and the Australian code for the responsible conduct of research*” [59].

In this section, sectoral requirements relevant to data retention and disposal and found in the *Australian Code for Responsible Conduct of Research (2018)* and guidelines related to human ethics, Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander research, and intellectual property are outlined.

5.1 Australian Code for Responsible Conduct of Research and the supporting Guide

The *Australian Code for Responsible Conduct of Research (2018)* [58] (referred to as “the Code” below) provides an overall framework based on broad principles and responsibilities that underpin the responsible conduct of research. Compliance with the Code is a requirement for receiving funding from the National Health and Medical Research Council and the Australian Research Council. Although the retention and disposal of research data are not

explicitly addressed in the Code, they fall under general principles relevant to good practices in access, disclosure, storage, retention, disposal, sharing and reuse of data:

- Principle 2: “Rigour in the development, undertaking and reporting of research”, which requires that researchers resort to reliable and established methodology to keep research methodology, data and findings;
- Principle 3: “Transparency in declaring interests and reporting research methodology, data and findings”, which requires that researchers be able to share and communicate research methodology, data and findings; and
- Principle 7: “Accountability for the development, undertaking and reporting of research”, which requires that researchers be aware of and comply with relevant legislation, policies and guidelines.

From these high-level principles, the Code articulates responsibilities of institutions and researchers. The associated guide *Management of Data and Information in Research: A guide supporting the Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research* [27] (referred to as “the Guide” below) deals explicitly with the storage, retention and disposal of research data and details institutions’ and researchers’ responsibilities.

Responsibility of institutions

The Guide states that, under the Code, institutions have the responsibility to “[d]evelop and maintain the currency and ready availability of a suite of policies and procedures which ensure that institutional practices are consistent with the principles and responsibilities of the Code” (responsibility of institutions R3). It is further added that institutional policies should include guidance both during and after a research project on:

- ownership, stewardship and control of research data;
- storage, retention and disposal of research data (whether held in an institutional repository or externally);
- safety, security and confidentiality of research data; and
- access to research data by interested parties.

The Guide further indicates that the storage, retention and disposal of research data should:

- be consistent with any copyright or licensing arrangements that are in place;
- be in accord with research discipline-specific practices and standards;
- comply with relevant privacy, ethical and publication requirements; and
- comply with other relevant laws, regulations and guidelines.

Importantly, the Guide recommends that data controlled by the institution or its researchers be stored in facilities provided by, or approved by, the institution that must comply with privacy requirements and other relevant laws, regulations, guidelines and standards related to safe and secure storage of data. Neither the Code nor the Guide provides explicit recommendation on the duration of the research data retention period but it is noted that the minimum retention period for research data is in general 5 years from the date of publication.

Responsibility of researchers

The main responsibility of researchers for research data retention and disposal is to “*retain*

clear, accurate, secure and complete records of all research including research data and primary materials” and “[w]here possible and appropriate, allow access and reference to these by interested parties” (responsibility of researchers R22). This implies that researchers should develop data management plans that detail how research data will be stored, why data may be used or disclosed and how access to data may be granted to third parties. The Guide recommends that researchers follow best practices to ensure that data are:

- retained in stable, safe and secure storage formats;
- retained in appropriate national and international standards for scientific terminology and information encoding;
- version-controlled; and
- appropriately documented regarding the algorithms, models, software (including configuration and version) and instruments used to generate, create, collect, process or analyse data.

The Guide recognises that while it may not be practical to keep all the primary material (for example, ore and biological material), durable records derived from them (for example, assays, test results and laboratory notes) must be retained and accessible. Importantly, the Guide states that researchers have primary responsibility for deciding which research data are candidates for long-term retention and wider accessibility. In addition to legislative requirements and requirements from funders, government bodies and publishers, the Guide provides criteria to consider in deciding which research data to retain:

- uniqueness and non-replicability;
- reliability, integrity, and usability;
- relevance to a known research initiative or collection;
- community, cultural or historical value; and
- economic benefit.

Finally, the Guide notes that research data can be the subject of freedom-of-information requests, and in such circumstances, there is an expectation that any information that is delivered will be provided in an understandable format and state.

5.2 Human ethics

The retention, storage and disposal of research data may be subject to ethical considerations besides the recommendations and requirements of the Code and the Guide. The *National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research 2007 (updated 2018)* [59] provides guidance on a range of topics before, during and after a research project. In particular, the document has two sections in Chapter 3.1 that are relevant here: “Collection, Use and Management of Data and Information” (Element 4) and “After the Project” (Element 7).

Element 4 deals with the generation, collection, access, use, analysis, disclosure, storage, retention, disposal, sharing and reuse of data. In particular, it is advised that:

- research data management plans address the retention, disposal, sharing and reuse of data, as well as the risks associated with these activities and any strategies for minimising the risks; and

- in collaborations, researchers agree on arrangements for the custodianship, storage, retention, destruction of data, and on the rights of access, use and reuse of data.

Element 7 focuses on researchers' ethical responsibilities after project completion for the disposal, retention and potential reuse of data, highlighting that researchers have ongoing ethical responsibilities when it comes to the retention, disposal or future use of data (including for the respectful disposal of data of cultural, historical or other significance).

5.3 Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander research

Data linked to Aboriginal people and Torres Strait Islander people may require to be kept, archived, destroyed and accessed via specific protocols to guarantee respect towards the people associated with the data as well as their families and communities. Note, the CARE principles for Indigenous data governance [7] aim to complement the FAIR principles by promoting data practices that are equitable to Indigenous people.

Several resources developed by Australian organisations deal with the management of Indigenous data with varied levels of advice specific to their retention and disposal; including:

- the *AIATSIS Code of Ethics for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Research* [60];
- the *Guide to Applying the AIATSIS Code of Ethics for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander* [61];
- the *Ethical conduct in research with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Peoples and communities: Guidelines for researchers and stakeholders* [62]; and
- the guide *Keeping research on track II* [63].

The Australian Institute of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Studies (AIATSIS) has developed documentation that provides advice and guidance on a range of topics. The *AIATSIS Code of Ethics for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Research* [60] promotes ethical and responsible practice in Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander research, in particular with regard to the “*creation, collection, analysis, interpretation, management, storage, dissemination, access, re-use, disposal of and access to*” data from or about Indigenous Australians (Principle 4: “Sustainability and accountability”). The associated document *Guide to Applying the AIATSIS Code of Ethics for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Research* [61] provides practical information on Indigenous data retention, disposal, storage and archiving.

The document *Ethical conduct in research with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Peoples and communities: Guidelines for researchers and stakeholders* [62] and its companion guide *Keeping research on track II* [63] developed by the National Health and Medical Research Council provide general advice to promote ethical, safe, respectful and responsible research with or for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people and communities, or their data or biological samples. Although there is no specific guideline on Indigenous research data retention or disposal, the guide recommends that agreements between researchers and Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander organisations and communities ensure that:

- research participants know where, how and for how long data are stored;
- data are returned to participants at the end of the storage period or destroyed; and
- the information collected is kept confidential and, where appropriate, de-identified.

5.4 Intellectual property

The *National Principles of Intellectual Property Management for Publicly Funded Research (2017)* [64] were developed to assist researchers, research managers and research institutions to develop best practices in identifying, protecting and managing intellectual property generated through research by public institutions and funded by the Australian Government. These principles have been adopted by the Australian Research Council and the National Health and Medical Research Council. In particular, it is required that research institutions develop policies to identify responsibilities for intellectual property management, including for the maintenance of research records (for example, electronic laboratory notebook and field notebooks) and the handling of research results prior to promoting and disseminating the intellectual property or obtaining intellectual property protection.

6 Institutional policies on research data retention and disposal

In this section, a few general observations on research data retention and disposal policies at research institutions are presented.

Public research institutions such as universities must retain and dispose of research data in accordance with legislative, ethical, sectoral and contractual requirements. However, the types of governance at those institutions and the associated frameworks organising data retention and disposal (policies, procedures, standards etc.) are heterogenous across the sector. This is due to various factors ranging from the amount and nature of research data created by each institution (for example, a significant part of research data may be clinical or associated with industry partners and, as a result, is subject to specific constraints) to different approaches taken to manage sensitive data.

The classification of data is an important factor in data retention and disposal as it determines the degree of sensitivity of data, thereby defining the modalities for their storage, backup and disposal to ensure that the confidentiality, integrity and availability of those data are maintained and protected. Compromises in confidentiality, integrity and availability of data expose them to significant risks for researchers and research institutions [29]. The security-based categorisation of research data (for example, highly sensitive–sensitive–public data) is not uniform across universities and does not necessarily follow or overlap with federal or relevant state or territory data classifications. For example, some universities have a three-tiered security classifications of data (for example, The Australian National University [65] and The University of Sydney [66]), whereas other universities have developed systems with four (for example, Monash University [67] and UNSW Sydney [68]), five (for example, The University of Queensland [69]) or six (for example, Curtin University [70]) security levels. The descriptions and the actions required by each tier may also differ between universities.

Furthermore, the policies and procedures on research data retention and disposal can be skewed towards institutional or enterprise records at some research institutions, which may seem too generic to be suitable or easily applicable to research data. The application of the records retention schedules issued by the Commonwealth, state and territories to determine the fate of research data also presents challenges. Records retention schedules use

assessment criteria that are based on some degree of *a posteriori* value judgement on research projects. Specifically, records retention schedules often differentiate research data (or records) in two main, mutually exclusive categories based on the quality of a project, its long-term impact and the researcher leading it. The first category often includes data associated with research of major national or international, disciplinary or wide-ranging significance; research of major national or international interest or controversy within the research community or beyond (for example, the society); research that involves the use of major, novel or innovative techniques; research that could have a major, long-term or lasting impact on the environment, society or human health; or research that is conducted by a principal investigator who is regarded as influential. These data are required to be retained permanently as national, state or territory archives. In contrast, the second category of research data consists of all other data that do not meet any of the criteria in the first category. This category is in general required to be retained temporarily with variations, for example whether the data are associated with a clinical trial or have led to a patent. As a result, a decision that research data can be eliminated after an arbitrary retention period because they are no longer required, are not part of a “significant” research project or not directly associated with a “significant” researcher may never appear justified. It is also in apparent contradiction with the very nature of research. Research builds slowly, empirically and sometimes chaotically or serendipitously upon previous data and knowledge. Yesterday’s seemingly valueless or artefactual data can be reused in tomorrow’s new, original, high-impact research project, or reinterpreted in the light of new knowledge or technology. The application of rule-based schedules, policies and procedures on the retention and disposal of research data is therefore complex for both institutions and researchers. However, it is important to note that, in general, there is no requirement for data and records to be eliminated at the expiration of their retention periods instructed by records retention schedules.

7 Awareness of microscopy facilities on research data retention and disposal

The general understanding of the concepts of retention and disposal of research data and how this translated into practices with regard to data storage, access to data and data security, were surveyed across microscopy facilities in Australia.

7.1 Method of the survey

The survey was conducted online from 2 to 19 September 2021 using Google Forms. The network of facilities associated with Microscopy Australia was leveraged to reach a large number of facilities across the country. In total, 21 microscopy facilities were invited to participate in the survey. 12 (57%) of the facilities contacted responded to the survey, which covered all the states and the Australian Capital Territory (Figure 4). Only one contribution per facility was considered. The contributions were provided by the directors or managers of the facilities, or staff in charge of research data management in general at the facilities.

The questions in the survey dealt with five main areas:

1. Awareness and training of staff at the facilities in data retention and disposal (survey questions Q1.1 to Q1.5).

2. The storage of data by the facilities (Q2.1 to Q2.4);
3. The nature of the storage service provided by the facilities (Q3.1 to Q3.7);
4. Access to the data stored by the facilities (Q4.1 to Q4.4); and
5. The storage procedures at the facilities (Q5.1 to Q5.6).

The details of the questions and the anonymised answers are provided in Appendix 1.

Note, the questions assumed no prior technical knowledge on the retention, disposal, storage or elimination of research data. Layperson’s language was employed in the survey questions. Some terms such as “deletion” of data should then be understood in their common acceptations, not in their specific, technical meaning. In this case, “deletion” referred to the generic action of removing or eliminating data and covered actions such as data destruction, data erasure, actual data deletion and device reformatting.

Figure 4 Geographic distribution of the microscopy facilities that participated in the survey.

7.2 Answers to the survey questions

Awareness and training of staff at the facilities in data retention and disposal

All the facilities surveyed were aware that the retention and disposal of research data were subject to specific provisions and legal requirements (survey question Q1.1, Appendix 1). Most facilities (85% in total) estimated their staffs had some level of knowledge (qualified as “average” or “good” by 46% and 39% of facilities, respectively, in Q1.2) about the requirements and responsibility of researchers, host universities and possibly facilities for research data retention and disposal. 15% of the facilities rated their staffs’ knowledge as “poor”.

Training in research data retention and disposal appeared to be a weak point overall. A clear majority of facilities (77%; Q1.3) was unaware of training being offered in this area by their organisations. In addition, 62% (Q1.4) answered that they had not received or been offered training by external organisations such as Microscopy Australia, Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) and the Australian National Imaging Facility (NIF) while only 15% declared that they had (23% were unsure). Among the facilities that had received or been offered training in research data retention and disposal by external organisations, Microscopy Australia was cited by all facilities and ARDC by half of them (Q1.5). Note, the fact that no facility had received training from NIF, the National Computational Infrastructure (NCI) or Pawsey

Supercomputing Centre may be due to the focus of the survey on microscopy facilities which may be outside the usual or natural audiences of these organisations.

Data storage at facilities

A majority (85%) of the facilities offered some form of storage for their users' data, including a short-term service with no guarantee on the reliability of the storage device or data integrity (question Q2.1). The storage service was primarily used to store raw data at all the facilities (Q2.2), but reduced data were often stored as well (73% of the facilities). Other types of data (such as data converted to different formats by users) were also stored at 18% of the facilities. The facilities that did not provide and did not plan to provide data storage answered that it was not their responsibility to offer storage (Q2.3, Q2.4).

The remainder of the survey focuses on facilities that provide data storage to their users.

Nature of the storage service provided by facilities

Among the facilities that stored their users' data, the storage periods given in question Q3.1 varied greatly and followed two main trends. On one hand, the majority of the facilities (64%) declared that they provided their users with some guarantee on the minimum period of time for the storage of their data: for a relatively fixed amount of time by about a quarter of the facilities (at least 2 or 6 months for 9% and 18% of the facilities, respectively), or, quite notably, indefinitely by a third (37%). On the other hand, the remaining third of the facilities gave their users either no guarantee (18% of the facilities) or no clear, predetermined storage period ("until storage space runs out"; 18%). Interestingly, no facility linked the extent of the storage period to the volume of data or the duration of users' projects.

Most facilities (73%) indicated that the storage of their users' data was safe (that is protected from loss and corruption) and secure (that is protected from unauthorised access) (Q3.2). 18% of the facilities said it was not while 9% were unsure.

The data storage service offered by facilities was in general the result of an internal decision by the facilities (Q3.3), either because they wished to provide their users with storage (36%) or because it was a facility policy to keep a copy of all data created (46%). For the other facilities (18%), data storage was mandated by their host universities.

Facilities often took advantage of the institutional storage media (Q3.4), either by convenience (28% of facilities) or because it was a university policy to use the organisational data stores (36%). However, 36% of the facilities preferred to use their own local storage media.

When storage was provided as a service by facilities, it was always intended as a temporary storage solution (Q3.5).

When data storage was required by host universities, half of the facilities were delegated responsibilities for the retention of their users' data but none of the facilities had any responsibility for the disposal of data (Q3.6 and Q3.7). Regarding the data stored, while 50% of the facilities were aware that the stored data were copies of their users' data, the other 50% did not know whether the stored data were copies or unique instances of users' data (Q3.8).

Access to data stored by facilities

Most facilities stored data via facility-owned accounts (55% of facilities; survey question Q4.1). The other main options were using the users' accounts or accounts created for users' projects by 27% and 9% of the facilities, respectively. A facility indicated that access to data was possible via various options provided users had university logins.

Access to data was more or less restricted at facilities (Q4.2). While 73% of the facilities indicated that users or the staff who assisted them had access to their data, access to users' data was in fact less restricted and allowed for all facility staff at 64% of the facilities and for all users at 36% of the facilities. In the latter case, facilities often commented that special arrangements were available for sensitive or confidential data. 27% of the facilities extended the access to a user's data to all the stakeholders of the user's project. Interestingly, no facility had users' data access permissions based on users' data management plans.

In general, users had access to their data stored by the facilities via two main modalities (Q4.3): the network of the host universities (82%) and portable storage devices, for example, flash drive and portable hard drive (55%). 27% of the facilities cited alternative ways instead of or in addition to these two main methods, such as access via a web portal, computers in the facilities and cloud services.

Data storage procedures at the facilities

Less than half of the facilities surveyed (45% in question 5.1) had their storage service described in a document such as general guidelines, facility use agreement or user's manuals. Even fewer facilities (27%; Q5.2) included such description in users' data management plans.

A majority of the facilities (55%) had special storage procedures for sensitive or confidential data (for example, data in projects that required ethics approval or in a collaboration with industry) (Q5.3). Most facilities (55%) knew if their users' data were subject to specific agreements or provisions such as ethics approval or industry partnership agreement (Q5.4).

Among the facilities that stored data for given periods of time (at least 2 or 6 months, Q3.1), a vast majority (80%) did not dispose of the data after the storage period had elapsed, that is, deleted the data, transferred them to the users or an internal or external party for longer storage or archiving (Q5.5).

Among the facilities that provided data storage as per facility policy, a majority (60%) did not have specific policies or guidelines for the retention and disposal of the copies of their users' data (Q5.6).

7.3 Outcome of the survey

The vast majority of the facilities that participated in the survey provided storage for their users' data. The main reason given was that facilities had the policy to keep a copy of all data that they created. Other reasons included that facilities wished to enhance their services or that storage of users' data was mandated by their host universities. Institutional storage solutions were often the preferred option to store users' data. The data consisted mostly of copies of raw and processed data.

The level of awareness that the retention and disposal of research data were associated with

specific actions and legislation was very high amongst the facilities. Similarly, there was some knowledge across facility staffs on the requirements and responsibilities that researchers, host universities and facilities may have for the retention and disposal of research data.

Most facilities offered safe and secure storage. The survey showed however that approaches to the handling of sensitive data, access to and disposal of stored data and documentation of the storage service were diverse across facilities and, in general, could be improved to encourage the adoption of best practices. Specifically, only about half of the facilities had special storage procedures for sensitive or confidential data or knew if their users' data were subject to specific agreements or provisions (for example, ethics approval and industry partnership agreement). Access to users' data was often relatively unrestricted allowing all staffs or any users at facilities to have access to all data linked to the facilities. In addition, there was no procedure for the systematic disposal of data at many facilities. Less than half of the facilities described the details of their data storage service in a document (for example, general guidelines, facility use agreement and user's manuals). The use of research data management plans to provide information on storage, retention and disposal of data (such as conditions for access to data) was remarkably limited.

8 Recommendations

In this chapter, general recommendations on the retention and disposal of research data are proposed to promote best practices across microscopy facilities. The recommendations are based on existing general guidelines and informed by the outcome of the survey presented in the previous chapter.

8.1 Data retention

If a microscopy facility stores its users' data temporarily or permanently, keeping more data than is required by legislation and sectoral or organisational policies and guidelines may be advised because some data may be needed in a near future. However, it is neither reasonable nor sustainable to keep everything. Therefore, the facility should adopt a selective approach and determine what data are worth retaining. A rule of thumb is to retain data that support publications or reports (including calibration data), may be reused or are irreproducible. It is in general not necessary to keep data from failed experiments, data that will not be used again or data that are easy to reproduce [35].

These considerations underscore the importance of a data retention policy that establishes protocols for keeping and disposing of data (Figure 5). A data retention policy should define:

- what data should be retained;
- the preferred format(s) in which data should be kept;
- the level of sensitivity required for data storage;
- how long data should be retained for;
- how data should be preserved;
- how data should be disposed of (for example, archived, destroyed, deleted);
- who has the authority to dispose of data; and
- rules to follow for breach, enforcement, and compliance.

Figure 5 Summary of the information provided in a facility's data retention policy, which is informed by various sources, including legislative, sectoral and organisational requirements as well as local and field-specific guidelines.

When a facility retains users' data permanently, the facility should have a data preservation strategy to maintain the value of data over time (accessibility, authenticity, integrity and usability) and to safeguard data against hardware and software obsolescence.

Note, although the primary purpose of a data retention policy is to ensure suitable data management, it is also an opportunity for a facility to enhance efficiency and sustainability in the storage of its users' data.

Recommendation 1: Data retention policy

Every facility should develop a data retention policy that details the rules and protocols for retaining and disposing of their users' data, in particular by addressing what data to retain, how to retain data and when to dispose of data.

8.2 Data disposal

Disposing of data properly is as important as retaining them because it improves [71]:

- data security: disposing of data appropriately ensures that sensitive data are not shared or made public;
- storage space: reducing the amount of data being stored lowers storage costs and contributes to the sustainability of storage for an organisation; and

- data searchability: disposing of data that are no longer needed makes finding relevant data easier for organisations and researchers.

Best practices dictate that disposal actions are mutually exclusive (Figure 1). Data are:

- transferred to an archiving service or institution for archiving; or
- transferred to a third party for further retention, alongside the custodianship or ownership of the data; or
- eliminated.

Therefore, it is recommended that a facility not keep a copy of its users' data after users have relocated (transferred) their data to their laboratories or chosen storage media, unless it is explicitly described in the data retention policy of the facility and made clear to users. In this case, the data retention policy should indicate that:

- users' data are kept for a fixed and explicit period of time after the completion of their experiments or after data have been transferred; or
- copies of users' data are kept permanently even after data have been transferred to users.

Recommendation 2: Data disposal — Extended retention of users' data

Every facility should eliminate their users' data after users have retrieved their data, unless the data retention policy of the facility describes explicitly and transparently how long users' data are retained for after their experiments.

Data elimination encompasses a range of actions with various levels of security as shown in Figure 1. Only destruction, erasure and masking can ensure that data cannot be recovered after their removal. Depending on the sensitivity of data, facilities should adapt their protocols for eliminating data. When users' data are not sensitive (for example, not clinical nor commercial), deletion is the quickest, easiest and most effective method to remove data. Note, suitable procedures for data elimination also apply to facilities that choose not to retain or store their users' data.

Recommendation 3: Data disposal — Suitable protocol for data elimination

Facilities should use appropriate methods to eliminate data, in particular in the case of sensitive data.

8.3 Data security and access to data

Users' data retained at facilities either temporarily or permanently (archived) should be stored in a way that ensures:

- confidentiality: users' data should only be made available to people in users' projects who are authorised to access them;
- integrity: users' data should be kept accurate, complete and unaltered (unless users are aware and have allowed changes); and

- availability: those who have access to a user's data should be able to do so when they need to.

Keeping data secure may involve a combination of systems and processes, such as [72]:

- applying controls which limit access to authorised personnel;
- monitoring security breaches; and
- using passwords for authentication.

Some of these systems and processes may be provided by institutional storage media used by facilities. It is however important that, in establishing strategies to protect data, data security and authentication mechanisms do not inadvertently make data inaccessible in the long term.

Recommendation 4: Data security and access to users' data

When facilities retain users' data, they should ensure that data remain accurate, complete and unaltered, and are accessible and available to authorised people only.

8.4 Data storage

Although data retention and data backup fulfil different purposes, they are often used interchangeably. As explained earlier (Figure 2), backing up data is a component of a data recovery plan whereas retaining data is part of a data retention policy. It is thus recommended that when a facility stores users' data, the purpose of this — backup, temporary retention or permanent retention (archive) — be clearly described in the data retention policy of the facility and communicated to users.

Recommendation 5: Storage of users' data

Facilities that store users' data should ensure that the purpose of the storage (backup, temporary retention, archive) is described in their data retention policies and communicated to their users.

8.5 File formats

Data retention provides mid- to long-term storage of inactive data so the preferred file formats for retained data are those that are unlikely to become obsolete. This condition minimises the risk of information loss due to the inability to read the files in the future, regardless of the retention period of data. The choice of sustainable file formats is also a trade-off between storage space and the level of compression of data (resulting in possible information loss). A “lossy” compression leads to small file sizes but a high risk of information loss whereas an uncompressed file format results in larger file sizes in exchange for a low risk of information loss. Drawing upon recommendations from various sources such as the Australasian Digital Recordkeeping Initiative [73], governments and record-keeping agencies (for example, Queensland Government [74] and State Records NSW [75]) and university libraries [76], a file format has a low risk of becoming obsolete and therefore be sustainable if it is:

- widely adopted: the format is used worldwide and supported by one or several communities;
- unrestricted: the format is non-proprietary (vendor-independent) and preferably open-source²;
- well-documented: the format is identifiable and its specification is publicly available and sufficiently detailed to be used and integrated into software for changes and read-and-write operations;
- stable: the format is stable (rare releases of newer versions) and is backward- and forward-compatible;
- platform-independent: the format is interoperable and supported by a wide range of software, developers and vendors;
- uncompressed: the format is ideally uncompressed or, if compression is used, lossless and non-proprietary compression is preferred;
- supported: technical support is readily available from, for example, communities of users, developers or vendors;
- unencrypted and not password-protected: the format is not protected by a password and is not encrypted (neither fully nor partially); and
- metadata-rich: the format has the ability to embed metadata.

A format can be considered sustainable even though it does not satisfy all these criteria. In general, the more criteria a format satisfies, the lower the risk of obsolescence. File formats that are widely adopted by a community may be considered de facto standard, but they may not be sustainable. For example, a file format that requires data and the related metadata be stored separately in different files cannot be considered sustainable. It may be manageable, but it is less likely to be easier to sustain over the long term and less vulnerable to information loss than a format that incorporates data and metadata in the same file.

In general, the use of sustainable file formats should not be restricted to the retention stage in the data lifecycle. It is recommended that sustainable file formats be used throughout the lifecycle from the creation or capture of data, or as early as possible in the lifecycle.

When no sustainable file format is available for a type of data, or the use of a sustainable format may not be feasible, practical or desired (for example, a file format that satisfies all the criteria above except the ability to embed metadata), it is advised to implement a strategy that ensures continued access to the data; for example, by retaining the programs, scripts and additional files necessary to access metadata and other information alongside the data.

Recommendation 6: Sustainable file formats

Data should be stored in sustainable file formats from their point of capture or creation in order to minimise the risk of information loss over time.

² The definitions for “open-source” and “non-proprietary” file formats are not identical. See the definition of open source by the Open Source Initiative (<https://opensource.org/osd>). There is also no widely accepted definition for “open formats”. Depending on the definition, an open format may require a fee to access its specification (“open proprietary”).

8.6 Data description

Retaining data is costly and time-consuming. While archiving takes care of dissemination, access control, security and preservation of data, it cannot be achieved efficiently without their adequate description through metadata. For example, a data owner can specify access restrictions in metadata (for example, a period of embargo until a given date after which data can be accessed). Similarly, an effective long-term data management strategy integrates curation as a core activity to maintain or enhance the value of data. This is facilitated by a rich description of data. Metadata (and persistent identifiers) enable the seamless integration of research administration and management systems throughout the data lifecycle. This can only be attained efficiently and sustainably by systematic, consistent and automated metadata capture in an ecosystem of interoperable research infrastructure [77].

Metadata should be collected continuously and as early as possible in the data lifecycle through multiple touchpoints (for example, grant application, human research ethics application, project creation, resource provisioning, raw-data capture). The contemporary capture and propagation of metadata alongside data throughout the data lifecycle promote accuracy and utility of data (for example, for reuse and sharing), and enable appropriate decisions to be made about curation, retention (storage, access control, sharing, reuse) and disposal of data [78]. They also contribute to determining the provenance and authenticity of data (for example, by identifying data creators and where data were created) and the accountability of record-keeping processes (for example, terms and conditions of access to, use and disposal of data) [79].

Metadata and persistent identifiers should be embedded in data. They should be used to describe a range of properties linked to data, including: publications and collections with a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) [80]; creators and contributors with an ORCID ID [81]; fields of research [82]; projects with a Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) [83]; and organisations with a Research Organization Registry (ROR) identifier [84]. Standardised metadata and persistent identifiers are recommended to allow data and projects to be managed across multiple systems at research institutions [77, 78].

Recommendation 7: Metadata collection

Metadata should be collected throughout the data lifecycle to facilitate and assist in the data curation, retention (storage, access control, sharing, reuse) and disposal.

8.7 Research data management plan

Users should have research data management plans (RDMPs) that describe how their data are stored, retained (temporarily or permanently), disposed of, preserved (in case of permanent retention), accessed and shared by facilities during and after experiments (Figure 6). Users' RDMPs are informed by the data retention policies of facilities. A range of questions should be addressed in a user's data management plan, including:

- how long will the user's data be retained for by the facility after an experiment?
- what type of data will be retained (for example, raw data, processed data)?

- who will have access to the user's data?
- how will access to data be provided?
- are there preferred file formats for retained data?
- what metadata will be collected?
- how will metadata be collected?
- when will the facility dispose of the user's data?
- how will the facility dispose of the user's data?
- how will the facility manage software and hardware obsolescence ?
- how will sensitive data be managed (for storage, disposal and access control)?

Recommendation 8: Research data management plan

Facility users should have research data management plans that describe the conditions for the storage, retention, disposal, access control and sharing of their data by facilities.

Figure 6 Information gathered in a research data management plan for users' data retention and disposal at a facility.

9 Conclusion

As research generates ever-growing volumes of data, keeping all data or copies of data unselectively has become impractical, impossible or too costly for many research organisations. Knowing what data to keep, how to store them and for how long is essential.

Suitable practices for research data retention and disposal can foster sustainable storage of data while ensuring that data remain valuable, authentic and shareable over time, as well as compatible with the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) and CARE (Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility and Ethics) principles. Data retention comprises the storage and management of data for a designated period of time beyond the completion of a research project and mandated by legal, regulatory, ethical, sectoral and contractual obligations of researchers and their host institutions. Data disposal refers to the processes associated with the destruction or transfer of data after this period of time. Practices in research data retention and disposal are diverse across microscopy research facilities: some facilities store their users' data for some time (with or without guarantee on the duration of the storage provided) or indefinitely, while other facilities do not store their users' data. However, in all cases, facilities have responsibilities for retaining and disposing of data appropriately.

In this report, general concepts pertaining to research data retention and disposal and relevant to microscopy facilities are presented alongside a brief outline of the legislative, sectoral and institutional landscape in research data retention and disposal. Eight recommendations are proposed to provide microscopy facilities with guidance and promote best practices in seven key areas in line with requirements from legislation and funding bodies: data retention policy; data disposal (after the retention of users' data and suitable protocol for data elimination); data security and access to users' data; storage of users' data; sustainable file formats for data retention; metadata collection; and research data management planning. Importantly, facilities can draw benefits from these recommendations by enhancing the efficiency and sustainability of their short- and long-term data storage, and increasing the long-term value and impact of the research that they enable through better data discoverability, reuse and sharing. In particular, the sustainable and systematic collection and embedding of metadata in research data can enable research data management and discoverability, and enhance the impact of the research that they are associated with.

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11 References

- 1 Baldwin, P. R., Tan, Y. Z., Eng, E. T., Rice, W. J., Noble, A. J., Negro, C. J., Cianfrocco, M. A., Potter, C. S., & Carragher, B. (2018). Big data in cryoEM: automated collection, processing and accessibility of EM data. *Current Opinion in Microbiology*, 43, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mib.2017.10.005>
- 2 Koh, A., Khavnekar, S., Yang, W., Karia, D., Cats, D., van der Ploeg, R., Grollios, F., Raschdorf, O., Kotecha, A., & Němeček, D. (2022). Routine Collection of High-Resolution cryo-EM Datasets Using 200 KV Transmission Electron Microscope. *Journal of Visualized Experiments: JoVE*(181), e63519. <https://doi.org/10.3791/63519>
- 3 Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg,

- N., Boiten, J.-W., da Silva Santos, L. B., Bourne, P. E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A. J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C. T., Finkers, R., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Gray, A. J. G., Groth, P., Goble, C., Grethe, J. S., Heringa, J., 't Hoen, P. A. C., Hooft, R., Kuhn, T., Kok, R., Kok, J., Lusher, S. J., Martone, M. E., Mons, A., Packer, A. L., Persson, B., Rocca-Serra, P., Roos, M., van Schaik, R., Sansone, S.-A., Schultes, E., Sengstag, T., Slater, T., Strawn, G., Swertz, M. A., Thompson, M., van der Lei, J., van Mulligen, E., Velterop, J., Waagmeester, A., Wittenburg, P., Wolstencroft, K., Zhao, J., & Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3(1), 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
- 4 Poger, D., Yen, L., & Braet, F. (2023). Big data in contemporary electron microscopy: challenges and opportunities in data transfer, compute and management. *Histochemistry and Cell Biology*, Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00418-023-02191-8>
 - 5 European Commission, & Directorate-General for Research Innovation. (2019). *Cost-benefit analysis for FAIR research data — Cost of not having FAIR research data*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2777/02999>
 - 6 Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. (2007). *OECD Principles and Guidelines for Access to Research Data from Public Funding*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264034020-en-fr>
 - 7 Carroll, S. R., Garba, I., Figueroa-Rodriguez, O. L., Holbrook, J., Lovett, R., Materechera, S., M., P., Raseroka, K., Rodrigues-Lonebear, D., Rowe, R., Sara, R., Walker, J. D., Anderson, J., & Hudson, M. (2020). The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance. *Data Science Journal*, 19(1), 43. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-043>
 - 8 Ackoff, R. L. (1989). From data to wisdom. *Journal of Applied Systems Analysis*, 16, 3–9.
 - 9 Williams, C. (2006). Principles and purposes of records and archives. In C. Williams (Ed.), *Managing Archives* (pp. 3–33). Chandos Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-1-84334-112-3.50002-9>
 - 10 National Archives of Australia. (n.d.). *Retaining, managing and disposing of data and datasets*. Retrieved July 10, 2023 from <https://www.naa.gov.au/information-management/disposing-information/retaining-managing-and-disposing-data-and-datasets>
 - 11 Rowley, J. (2007). The wisdom hierarchy: representations of the DIKW hierarchy. *Journal of Information Science*, 33(2), 163–180. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0165551506070706>
 - 12 Standards Australia. (2017). *AS ISO 15489.1:2017, Information and documentation — Records management, Part 1: Concepts and principles*. Standards Australia. <https://store.standards.org.au/product/as-iso-15489-1-2017>
 - 13 The University of Melbourne. (2011). *Management of Research Data and Records Policy (MPF1242)*. <https://policy.unimelb.edu.au/MPF1242>
 - 14 Kennan, M. A., & Markauskaite, L. (2015). Research Data Management Practices: A Snapshot in Time. *International Journal of Digital Curation*, 10(2), 70–95. <https://doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v10i2.329>
 - 15 State Records NSW. (2003, January, 2023). *Glossary of Recordkeeping Terms*. Retrieved July 10, 2023 from <https://staterecords.nsw.gov.au/recordkeeping/guidance-and-resources/glossary-recordkeeping-terms>
 - 16 Grant, R. (2017). Recordkeeping and research data management: a review of perspectives. *Records Management Journal*, 27(2), 159–174. <https://doi.org/10.1108/RMJ-10-2016-0036>
 - 17 Queensland Government. (2021). *About retention and disposal schedules*. Retrieved July 10, 2023 from <https://www.forgov.qld.gov.au/information-and-communication-technology/recordkeeping-and-information-management/recordkeeping/retention-disposal-and-destruction-of-records/about-retention-and-disposal-schedules>
 - 18 National Archives of Australia. (n.d.). *Records authorities*. Retrieved July 10, 2023 from <https://www.naa.gov.au/information-management/records-authorities>
 - 19 Imperva Inc. (n.d.). *Data Sanitization*. Retrieved July 10, 2023 from <https://www.imperva.com/learn/data-security/data-sanitization>
 - 20 International Data Sanitization Consortium. (n.d.). *Data Sanitization Terminology and Definitions*. Retrieved July 10, 2023 from <https://www.datasanitization.org/data-sanitization-terminology>
 - 21 Office of the Australian Information Commissioner. (2018). *De-identification and the Privacy Act*. Office of the Australian Information Commissioner, Commonwealth of Australia. Retrieved from <https://www.oaic.gov.au/privacy/guidance-and-advice/de-identification-and-the-privacy-act>
 - 22 Regulation 2016/679. *Regulation (EU) No 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal*

- data and the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)*. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>
- 23 Cobb, M. (2022, September). *Data masking*. TechTarget. Retrieved July 10, 2023 from <https://www.techtarget.com/searchsecurity/definition/data-masking>
- 24 Australasian Digital Recordkeeping Initiative. (2022). *ADRI Glossary of disposal triggers (Exposure draft)*. Council of Australasian Archives and Records Authorities. <https://www.caara.org.au/index.php/working-groups/adri/products/transferring-digital-records-to-archives-and-records-authorities/>
- 25 Williams, C. (2006). Selection, appraisal and acquisition. In C. Williams (Ed.), *Managing Archives* (pp. 35–69). Chandos Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-1-84334-112-3.50003-0>
- 26 State Archives and Records Authority of New South Wales. (2017). *General retention and disposal authority: higher and further education (GA47)*. State Archives and Records Authority of New South Wales, Government of New South Wales. Retrieved from <https://staterrecords.nsw.gov.au/sites/default/files/Recordkeeping/GA0047%20Higher%20and%20further%20education%20August%202019.pdf>
- 27 National Health and Medical Research Council, Australian Research Council, & Universities Australia. (2019). *Management of Data and Information in Research: A guide supporting the Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research*. National Health and Medical Research Council, Commonwealth of Australia. Retrieved from <https://www.nhmrc.gov.au/sites/default/files/documents/attachments/Management-of-Data-and-Information-in-Research.pdf>
- 28 Hart, E. M., Barnby, P., LeBauer, D., Michonneau, F., Mount, S., Mulrooney, P., Poisot, T., Woo, K. H., Zimmerman, N. B., & Hollister, J. W. (2016). Ten Simple Rules for Digital Data Storage. *PLoS Computational Biology*, 12(10), e1005097. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1005097>
- 29 Attorney-General's Department. (2018). *Protective Security Policy Framework – Policy 8: Sensitive and classified information*. Attorney-General's Department, Commonwealth of Australia. Retrieved from <https://www.protectivesecurity.gov.au/system/files/2023-01/pspf-policy-08-sensitive-and-classified-information.pdf>
- 30 National Archives of Australia. (n.d.). *Cloud computing and information management*. Retrieved July 10, 2023 from <https://www.naa.gov.au/information-management/storing-and-preserving-information/storing-information/cloud-computing-and-information-management>
- 31 National Archives of Australia. (n.d.). *Outsourcing digital storage*. Retrieved July 10, 2023 from <https://www.naa.gov.au/information-management/storing-and-preserving-information/storing-information/outsourcing-digital-storage>
- 32 Darch, P. T., Sands, A. E., Borgman, C. L., & Golshan, M. S. (2020). Library cultures of data curation: Adventures in astronomy. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 71(12), 1470–1483. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.24345>
- 33 Pacific Data Hub Microdata Library. (n.d.). *What is Data Curation and Preservation?* Retrieved July 10, 2023 from <https://microdata.pacificdata.org/index.php/policy-and-procedures>
- 34 Queensland Government. (2021). *Digital records, storage media and systems*. Retrieved July 10, 2023 from <https://www.forgov.qld.gov.au/information-and-communication-technology/recordkeeping-and-information-management/recordkeeping/store-protect-and-care-for-records/store-protect-and-care-for-digital-records/digital-records-storage-media-and-systems#preserv>
- 35 Briney, K. (2015). *Data management for researchers : organize, maintain and share your data for research success*. Pelagic Publishing.
- 36 Monash University. (n.d.). *Legislative Requirements – Records Archives*. Retrieved July 10, 2023 from <https://www.monash.edu/records-archives/records-management/policy-and-procedure/legislative-requirements>
- 37 *Therapeutic Goods Regulations 1990* (Cth). <https://www.legislation.gov.au/Series/F1996B00406>
- 38 International Council for Harmonisation of Technical Requirements for Pharmaceuticals for Human Use (ICH). (2016). *Integrated Addendum to ICH E6(R1): Guideline for Good Clinical Practice ICH E6(R2)*. Retrieved from <https://www.tga.gov.au/resources/publication/publications/ich-guideline-good-clinical-practice>
- 39 *Privacy Act 1988* (Cth). <https://www.legislation.gov.au/Series/C2004A03712>
- 40 *Archives Act 1983* (Cth). <https://www.legislation.gov.au/Details/C2016C00772/>
- 41 *Australian National University Act 1991* (Cth). <https://www.legislation.gov.au/Details/C2014C00377>
- 42 National Archives of Australia. (2007). *Records Authority – Australian National University 2006/00446555*. National Archives of Australia, Commonwealth of Australia. Retrieved from

- <https://www.naa.gov.au/sites/default/files/2019-12/agency-ra-2006-00446555.pdf>
- 43 *Territory Records Act 2002* (ACT). <https://www.legislation.act.gov.au/a/2002-18/>
- 44 Territory Records Office. (2007). *Records Disposal Schedule – Tertiary Teaching and Research Records*. Territory Records Office, ACT Government. Retrieved from <https://www.legislation.act.gov.au/ni/2007-314/>
- 45 *State Records Act 1998* (NSW). <https://www.records.nsw.gov.au/about/state-records-act-1998>
- 46 *Information Act 2002* (NT). <https://legislation.nt.gov.au/en/LegislationPortal/Acts/~link.aspx?id=E3D76300FE5F4C48B00676292C67ADBC&z=z&format=assented>
- 47 Northern Territory Archives Services, & Northern Territory Records Services. (2017). *Disposal Schedule for Research Management Records of the Charles Darwin University (No. 2017/14)*. Northern Territory Records Services, Northern Territory Government. Retrieved from https://tffc.nt.gov.au/_data/assets/pdf_file/0011/457409/disposal-schedule-2017-14-cdu-research-management.pdf
- 48 *Public Records Act 2002* (Qld). <https://www.legislation.qld.gov.au/view/html/inforce/current/act-2002-011>
- 49 Queensland State Archives. (2014). *University Sector Retention and Disposal Schedule (QDAN: 601v.3)*. Queensland State Archives, Queensland Government. Retrieved from <https://www.forgov.qld.gov.au/schedules/university-sector-retention-and-disposal-schedule>
- 50 *State Records Act 1997* (SA). <https://www.legislation.sa.gov.au/LZ/C/A/STATE%20RECORDS%20ACT%201997.aspx>
- 51 State Records of South Australia. (2017). *General Disposal Schedule No. 24 Version 5 – South Australian Universities (GDS 24)*. State Records of South Australia, Government of South Australia. Retrieved from https://www.archives.sa.gov.au/_data/assets/pdf_file/0007/918133/GDS-24-v5-South-Australian-Universities-General-Disposal-Schedule.pdf
- 52 *Archives Act 1983* (Tas). <https://www.legislation.tas.gov.au/view/html/inforce/current/act-1983-076>
- 53 Tasmanian Archive and Heritage Office. (2012). *Disposal Schedule for Functional records of the University of Tasmania (Disposal Authorisation No. 2398; DA 2398)*. Office of the State Archivist, Tasmanian Government. Retrieved from <https://www.informationstrategy.tas.gov.au/Publications/Document%20Library%20%20RDS/University%20of%20Tasmania.pdf>
- 54 *Public Records Act 1973* (Vic). <https://www.legislation.vic.gov.au/in-force/acts/public-records-act-1973/041>
- 55 Public Record Office Victoria. (2019). *Retention and Disposal Authority for Records of Higher and Further Education Functions (authority number: PROS 16/07)*. Public Record Office Victoria, State Government of Victoria. Retrieved from <https://prov.vic.gov.au/recordkeeping-government/document-library/pros-1607-higher-and-further-education-functions>
- 56 *State Records Act 2000* (WA). https://www.legislation.wa.gov.au/legislation/statutes.nsf/law_a2037.html
- 57 State Records Office of Western Australia. (2013). *Western Australia University Sector Disposal Authority (Disposal Authority No 2022-005)*. State Records Office of Western Australia, Government of Western Australia. Retrieved from <https://www.wa.gov.au/system/files/2022-08/WAUSDA%202022-005.pdf>
- 58 National Health and Medical Research Council, Australian Research Council, & Universities Australia. (2018). *Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research*. National Health and Medical Research Council, Commonwealth of Australia. Retrieved from <https://www.nhmrc.gov.au/about-us/publications/australian-code-responsible-conduct-research-2018>
- 59 National Health and Medical Research Council, Australian Research Council, & Universities Australia. (2018). *National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research 2007 (Updated 2018)*. National Health and Medical Research Council, Commonwealth of Australia. Retrieved from www.nhmrc.gov.au/guidelines/publications/e72
- 60 Australian Institute of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Studies. (2020). *AIATSIS Code of Ethics for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Research*. Australian Institute of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Studies. Retrieved from <https://aiatsis.gov.au/research/ethical-research/code-ethics>
- 61 Australian Institute of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Studies. (2020). *Guide to Applying the AIATSIS Code of Ethics for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Research*. Australian Institute of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Studies. Retrieved from <https://aiatsis.gov.au/research/ethical-research/code-ethics>
- 62 National Health and Medical Research Council. (2018). *Ethical conduct in research with Aboriginal*

- and Torres Strait Islander Peoples and communities: Guidelines for researchers and stakeholders. National Health and Medical Research Council, Commonwealth of Australia. Retrieved from <https://www.nhmrc.gov.au/about-us/resources/ethical-conduct-research-aboriginal-and-torres-strait-islander-peoples-and-communities>
- 63 National Health and Medical Research Council. (2018). *Keeping research on track II: A companion document to Ethical conduct in research with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Peoples and communities: Guidelines for researchers and stakeholders*. National Health and Medical Research Council, Commonwealth of Australia. Retrieved from <https://www.nhmrc.gov.au/about-us/resources/keeping-research-track-ii>
- 64 Australian Research Council. (2022). *National Principles of Intellectual Property Management for Publicly Funded Research (last updated 16/06/2022)*. Australian Research Council, Commonwealth of Australia. Retrieved from <https://www.arc.gov.au/policies-strategies/policy/national-principles-intellectual-property-management-publicly-funded-research>
- 65 The Australian National University. (2019). *Infrastructure security classification*. https://policies.anu.edu.au/ppl/document/ANUP_000753
- 66 The University of Sydney. (2020). *Cybersecurity Standard – Data Classification*.
- 67 Monash University. (2017). *Electronic Information Security – Information Classification Procedure*. <https://publicpolicydms.monash.edu/Monash/documents/1909276>
- 68 UNSW Sydney. (2021). *Data Classification Standard*. <https://www.unsw.edu.au/content/dam/pdfs/governance/policy/2022-01-policies/datastandard.pdf>
- 69 The University of Queensland. (2021). *Information Security Classification Procedure*. <https://ppl.app.uq.edu.au/content/6.40.02-information-security-classification>
- 70 Curtin University. (2020). *Information Security Classification Policy*. https://policies.curtin.edu.au/local/docs/policy/Information_Security_Classification_Policy.pdf
- 71 National Archives of Australia. (n.d.). *Information disposal*. Retrieved July 10, 2023 from <https://www.naa.gov.au/information-management/disposing-information/information-disposal>
- 72 National Archives of Australia. (n.d.). *Protecting information*. Retrieved July 10, 2023 from <https://www.naa.gov.au/information-management/protecting-information>
- 73 Australasian Digital Recordkeeping Initiative. (2020). *Sustainable Digital Formats for Creating and Using Records*. Council of Australasian Archives and Records Authorities. <https://www.caara.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/Sustainable-Digital-File-Formats-for-Creating-and-Using-Records-V1.0-April-2020.pdf>
- 74 Queensland Government. (2021, 5 May). *File formats for long-term digital records*. Retrieved July 10, 2023 from <https://www.forgov.qld.gov.au/information-and-communication-technology/recordkeeping-and-information-management/recordkeeping/store-protect-and-care-for-records/store-protect-and-care-for-digital-records/file-formats-for-long-term-digital-records>
- 75 State Records NSW. (2019). *Sustainable file formats*. Retrieved July 10, 2023 from <https://staterecords.nsw.gov.au/recordkeeping/guidance-and-resources/sustainable-file-formats>
- 76 University of Oregon Libraries. (2022, September 13). *File Format Standards*. University of Oregon. Retrieved July 10, 2023 from <https://researchguides.uoregon.edu/data-management/fileformats>
- 77 Poger, D. (2023). *Metadata collection at microscopy research facilities: Overview and recommendations*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7949932>
- 78 Australian Research Data Commons. (2023). *Research data management framework for institutions*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7655308>
- 79 Cumming, K. (2007). Purposeful data: The roles and purposes of recordkeeping metadata. *Records Management Journal*, 17(3), 186–200. 10.1108/09565690710833099
- 80 DOI Foundation. (n.d.). *What is a DOI?* Retrieved July 10, 2023 from <https://www.doi.org/the-identifier/what-is-a-doi/>
- 81 ORCID. (n.d.). *About ORCID*. Retrieved July 10, 2023 from <https://info.orcid.org/what-is-orcid/>
- 82 Australian Bureau of Statistics. (2020). *Australian and New Zealand Standard Research Classification (ANZSRC)*. Retrieved July 10, 2023 from <https://www.abs.gov.au/statistics/classifications/australian-and-new-zealand-standard-research-classification-anzsrc/latest-release>
- 83 Research Activity Identifier (RAiD). (n.d.). *Identify and track your research projects and activities with RAiD*. Retrieved July 10, 2023 from <https://www.raid.org.au>
- 84 ROR. (n.d.). *What is ROR?* Retrieved July 10, 2023 from <https://ror.org/about/>

APPENDIX 1

Survey on Research Data Retention and Disposal at Microscopy Facilities

A1 Awareness and training in data retention and disposal

1.1 Are facilities aware that specific provisions and legal requirements may apply to the retention and disposal of research data?

1.2 How do facilities rate the knowledge among their staff in requirements and responsibility that researchers, the host universities and, possibly, their facilities have in research data retention and disposal?

1.3 Do the universities hosting facilities offer training in research data retention and disposal?

1.4 Have facilities received or been offered training on research data retention and disposal by one or several external organisation(s), including (and not limited to) the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC), Microscopy Australia and the Australian National Imaging Facility (NIF)?

Among the facilities that have received or been offered training on research data retention and disposal...

1.5 Which of the following external organisations have offered facilities training on research

data retention and disposal?

A2 Data storage by facilities

2.1 Do facilities offer any form of storage of their users' data, including as a short-term (temporary) service with no guarantee of retrieving any data in case of data loss, data corruption or device malfunction?

Among the facilities that do not provide data storage...

2.2 Why do they not offer any form of data storage to their users?

2.3 Would they be interested in providing a data storage service to their users?

Among the facilities that provide data storage...

2.4 What type(s) of research data do facilities store?

A3 Nature of the storage services provided by facilities

3.1 How long do facilities store users' data for?

3.2 Are users' data stored in a way that is safe (that is protected from loss and corruption) and secure (that is protected from unauthorised access)?

3.3 Why do facilities store users' data?

3.4 Where do facilities store users' data?

Among the facilities that provide data storage as a service...

3.5 Is the storage service intended as temporary storage (for example, as a temporary backup for data or until users have transferred their data to their laboratories or home organisations)?

Among the facilities that provide data storage as per university policy...

3.6 Have the host universities delegated to the facilities any responsibility in terms of data retention (for example, by ensuring that the integrity of the data is maintained over time)?

3.7 Have the host universities delegated to the facilities any responsibility in terms of data disposal after a given retention time (for example, by deleting data or transferring data to internal or external parties for longer storage or archiving)?

3.8 Are the data stored in addition to the users' copies of their data?

A4 Access to the data stored by facilities

4.1 What accounts are used by facilities to store users' data?

4.2 Who has access to users' data stored by facilities?

4.3 How do users access their data stored by facilities?

A5 Storage procedures at the facilities

5.1 Are the details of the storage service provided described in documents issued by facilities (for example, general guidelines, facility use agreement and user's manuals)?

5.2 Are the details of the storage service provided by facilities described in users' data management plans?

5.3 Do facilities have special storage procedures for sensitive or confidential data (for example, data generated from a project that required ethics approval or from a collaboration with industry)?

5.4 Do facilities know if the stored users' data are subject to specific agreements or provisions (for example, ethics approval or partnership agreement with industry)?

Among the facilities that store data for given periods of time (see question 3.1)...

5.5 Are data systematically disposed of after those periods (that is deleted, transferred to the users or an internal or external party for longer storage or archiving)?

Among the facilities that provide data storage as per facility policy (see question 3.5)...

5.6 Have facilities developed specific policies or guidelines for the retention and disposal of the copies of users' data?

